

INITIAL DATA FOR THE VALUES OF THE ELECTROCARDIOGRAM ELEMENTS IN CLINICALLY HEALTHY OBESE CATS

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ABSTRACT

We present statistically processed initial data on all elements of ECG and also for the electrical axis and the systolic index in clinically healthy cats with obesity. These values are compared to values obtained from clinically healthy cats with a normal body weight. The number of individuals from each group is, as follows: 6 cats with obesity and 21 cats with a normal body weight.

Key words: ECG, ECG diversion, ECG values, obesity, cats.

Introduction

Kostov (1995) suggested 12 cardiac leads located in a semi-sagittal plain, which we have also applied (standard and unipolar leads) in the recordings made in both groups.

Tilley (1992) was recording standard ECG leads in dogs and cats as putting the animals in the right-lying position. The electrodes (clamps-crocodiles) are placed on the chest limbs in the area behind the elbow and the pelvic limbs in the area of the knee fold. With this electrode position, it could be assumed that the average leads are in a horizontal (frontal) plain.

From the record of normal ECG in cats taken from the forelimb and under thigh areas by the same author, shown in the figure was visible that the T wave is negative in standard leads I and II.

Martin (2005) was using for ECG recording in cats, except the lateral lying position and sitting position of the body by attaching adhesive electrodes or metal plates to the distal parts of the limbs.

Electrocardiographic data on the amplitude and duration of individual ECG elements in cats were published by Tilley (1992). The average heart rate is 197 min^{-1} and varies between $120\text{--}240 \text{ min}^{-1}$. In the standard lead II, the P-wave did not exceed height of 0.2 mV and duration of 0.04 s. The QRS complex reached 0.9 mV and duration is 0.04 s. The T-wave reached an amplitude of 0.3 mV. The electric axis of the heart in the frontal plain extended from 0° to $\pm 160^\circ$.

Lourenco and Ferreira (2003) defined the parameters of the normal waves of the electrocardiogram in clinically healthy newborn kittens. 15 males and 15 female kittens up to 30 days of age were studied. The analyzed parameters were heart rate and heart rhythm, duration and amplitude of the ECG waves, intervals and the electric axis of the heart. The results did not show a difference in the values between males and females. In the period from birth to 30 days, the electric axis shifted away from right to left, the amplitude of the R-wave gradually raised up and that of the S-wave gradually decreased. The sinus rhythm dominated in newborn kittens.

A data of heart rate and ECG elements in cats was reported by Martin (2005), which are: $160\text{--}240 \text{ min}^{-1}$ an amplitude and duration of the P-wave, shorter than 0.2 mV and less than 0.04 s; P-Q complex 0.05–0.09 s; an amplitude and duration of R-wave shorter than 0.9 mV and less than 0.04 s; the amplitude of T-wave shorter than 0.3 mV; Q-T interval 0.12 – 0.18 s and average electric axis of the heart from 0° to $+ 160^\circ$.

Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) and other forms of cardiomyopathy are common diseases in cats. One of the most important aspects of optimal care for animals with heart failure is

maintaining optimal weight and body condition. As in dogs and people, cats can lose body weight and lean body mass (ie, cardiac cachexia) which may negatively affect immune function, strength, and mortality. The direct relationship between weight or body mass index (BMI) and survival time has been called the “obesity paradox.” (Finn et al, 2010).

Lund et al (2005), using a cross-sectional study design, the prevalence of overweight and obesity in adult cats seen by US veterinarians during 1995 was determined. Risk factors for overweight and obesity were also determined from the following variables: age, breed, gender, body condition score, food type, reported concurrent disease, and geographic region. Thirty-five percent of adult cats (n = 8,159) were overweight or obese. The relationship of obesity to the development of disease in cats is of much clinical interest but has been the subject of limited research.

Obesity is the most common nutritional disorder of cats and is a risk factor for diabetes. Similar to developments in obese people, obese cats show peripheral tissue insulin resistance and may demonstrate glucose intolerance when challenged with pharmacological amounts of glucose. Cats do not develop atherosclerosis and clinical hypertension (Hoenig, 2012).

According to Pereira-Neto et al (2010), obesity is one of the most frequent nutritional problems in companion animals and can lead to severe health problems in dogs and cats, such as cardiovascular diseases. This research aimed to evaluate the structural and functional cardiac changes after weight loss in obese dogs. The M-mode echocardiogram, electrocardiogram, and blood pressure evaluations were performed before the diet has started and after the dogs have reached the target weight. The weight loss program can reverse structural cardiac changes such as left ventricle eccentric hypertrophy in dogs weighing more than 30 kg, and decrease the arterial blood pressure in obese dogs.

For the electrocardiography recording dogs were positioned in right lateral recumbency and the electrode clips were attached to the animal’s skin in the standard positions as described by Tilley (1995). The electrocardiogram analysis was obtained from lead II. The authors measured the following parameters: duration of P wave (Pms), P wave amplitude (PmV), duration of PR interval (PRms), duration of QRS complex (QRSms), R wave amplitude (RmV), duration of QT interval (QTms), ST segment amplitude (ST), T wave amplitude (T), mean electrical axis, heart rate (HR) and heart rhythm.

The computerized electrocardiographic evaluation initially showed an increase in mean P wave duration for 100%, 40% and 20% of the dogs in groups I, II and III, respectively, compared with normal values for computerized electrocardiography in literature (Wolf et al. 2000), this data could indicate alteration in an electrical conduction through the atria in obese dogs, but further studies are necessary to prove this hypothesis. After weight reduction, a decrease in duration was observed in all groups, differing from that reported in morbid obese humans. (Pereira-Neto et al, 2010).

Materials and Methods

For the initial studies, 6 clinically healthy obese cats were used (in the study group, all animals were neutered). The average age of the studied animals was over 10 years, most of them were female. The weight of the animals varied between 4.500 to 6.500 kg, averaging about 5.800 kg.

Purposefully, animals that completely meet the purpose of our research, were searched for and examined.

The electrocardiogram recording was performed with 12 channel ECG devices – EKG – 1233 and ECG – BG, 1262. The band speed was 50 mm / s, calibration of the unit by height from the isoelectric line was 1 mV = 1 cm. All records were made when the "Filter" function on the devices was turned on. Needle electrodes, which were placed subcutaneously after disinfection at the determined points, were used for leading of biopotentials from the heart.

Heart leads were made based on stationary leads in Kostov (1995) as the electrode with a red marking was placed on the right of the neck in front of the front edge of scapula. and the electrode with a yellow mark on the left in the area of the heart at the level of the elbow outgrowth. The green-marked electrode was placed on the left in the area of the horizontal line dividing the chest with the perpendicularly lowered from the last rib. The patient's ground electrode (black) was placed on one of the knee folds. In this way, the standard leads are registered as I, II, and III, and unipolar (enlarged) leads – as aVR, aVL, and aVF.

The results of the studies were processed using variation statistics methods. The average values (x avg.) were calculated. Differences with $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results

The data values of the elements of ECG clinically healthy obese cats are presented in Table 1, as they are compared with the values of the parameters of ECG in clinically healthy cats without obesity (Table 2).

The data shown in Tables 1 and 2 shows that the heart rate in the group of obese cats was in the range of $188.00 \pm 6.39 \text{ min}^{-1}$, which was almost equal to that in the group without obesity ($183.92 \pm 7.39 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The same was applied for the R-R interval, compared in both groups ($0.32 \pm 0.011 \text{ s}$ in $0.34 \pm 0.013 \text{ s}$).

The amplitude of the P-wave was the highest in the II and aVR standard leads, which was $0.116 \pm 0.006 \text{ mV}$, and the lowest in aVL discharge $0.050 \pm 0.007 \text{ mV}$. A similar trend in such heart leads was also observed in the length of the P-wave - $0.040 \pm 0.002 \text{ s}$ at $0.030 \pm 0.002 \text{ s}$.

The direction in the results for the amplitude and duration of the P-wave in the same leads of the animals without obesity was similar, where the values of the indexes are very close to these in the group with obesity.

The values of the P-Q segment were $0.040 \pm 0.002 \text{ s}$ to leads I, II and aVR to $0.043 \pm 0.002 \text{ s}$ to leads III, aVL and aVF that were not significant increased compared to the group of animals without obesity.

The P-Q interval was varied in a narrow range in the different heart leads from $0.073 \pm 0.003 \text{ s}$ in aVL taking to $0.080 \pm 0.003 \text{ s}$ in the standard leads II, aVR and aVF.

The trend for the P-Q interval compared in the two groups followed that described for the P-Q segment length values.

In some of the animals in both groups, a presence of Q-wave in the leads I, II, aVL and aVF was registered.

The amplitude of the R-wave was highest in the standard lead I $0.376 \pm 0.022 \text{ mV}$, close to this value in the lead II $0.366 \pm 0.025 \text{ mV}$ and was absent in lead aVR. Close to these were the values for this indicator in the standard leads I and II in the second group of cats with normal weight ($0.377 \pm 0.027 \text{ mV}$, 0.367 ± 0.027).

The length R-wave was the highest and the same in the first two standard leads 0.040 ± 0.002 s, and lower in the other leads. In all leads, this indicator was lower in the non-obese group of cats.

Table 1: Values of ECG elements in clinically healthy obese cats

Parameters	Leads					
	I	II	III	aVR	aVL	aVF
Number of animals/n/	6					
Heart rate (min ⁻¹)	188.00 ± 6.38					
R–R interval (s)	0.32 ± 0.011					
P-wave (mV)	0.083 ± 0.005	0.116 ± 0.006	0.050 ± 0.009	0.116 ± 0.004	0.050 ± 0.007	0.100 ± 0.009
P-wave (s)	0.036 ± 0.001	0.040 ± 0.002	0.030 ± 0.004	0.040 ± 0.002	0.030 ± 0.002	0.036 ± 0.003
P–Q segment (s)	0.040 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.002	0.043 ± 0.004	0.040 ± 0.002	0.043 ± 0.002	0.043 ± 0.002
P–Q interval (s)	0.076 ± 0.003	0.080 ± 0.003	0.076 ± 0.004	0.080 ± 0.003	0.073 ± 0.003	0.080 ± 0.004
Q-wave (mV)	6/0.050				6/0.050	2/0.050
R-wave (mV)	0.376 ± 0.027	0.366 ± 0.027	0.150 ± 0.046	0.366 ± 0.021		0.266 ± 0.029
R-wave (s)	0.040 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.002	0.030 ± 0.004			0.036 ± 0.002
S-wave (mV)			2/0.150 ± 0.032	0.366 ± 0.021	2/0.100 ± 0.062	
S–T segment (s)	0.063 ± 0.002	0.063 ± 0.002	0.063 ± 0.003	0.063 ± 0.003	0.063 ± 0.002	0.063 ± 0.003
Q–T interval (s)	0.156 ± 0.004	0.160 ± 0.005	0.156 ± 0.007	0.156 ± 0.004	0.156 ± 0.002	0.160 ± 0.006
T-wave (mV)	+ 0.116 ± 0.017	+ 0.133 ± 0.010	+ 0.100 ± 0.010	- 0.100 ± 0.014	+0.100 ± 0.015	+ 0.116 ± 0.009
T-wave (s)	0.043 ± 0.003	0.050 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.003	0.043 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.003	0.046 ± 0.002
T–P segment (s)	0.060 ± 0.011	0.060 ± 0.009	0.060 ± 0.017	0.060 ± 0.010	0.060 ± 0.015	0.060 ± 0.012
Systolic indicator %	48.75					
Electric axis	+ 43°					

The presence of S-wave was recorded in leads III, aVR (with the highest amplitude) and aVF.

The variability is greater in the S-T segment which was 0.063 ± 0.002 s for all heart leads, and in the group of clinically healthy non-obese cats.

The Q–T interval in leads II standard and aVF was 0.160 ± 0.004 s, with similar values for other heart leads, as well as values for the indicator in the normal group of animals.

In the various heart leads, are latively low amplitude of T-wave was recorded. It reached 0.133 ± 0.011 mV in the lead standard II, which is close to the values in the other heart leads, as well as the values in the leads in the second group of non-obese.

Table 2: Values of the parameters of ECG in clinically healthy cats without obesity

Parameters	Leads					
	I	II	III	aVR	aVL	aVF
Number of animals/n/	21					
Heart rate (min ⁻¹)	183.92 ± 7.39	183.92 ± 7.39	183.92 ± 7.39	183.92 ± 7.39	183.92 ± 7.39	183.92 ± 7.39
R-R interval (s)	0.34 ± 0.013	0.34 ± 0.013	0.34 ± 0.013	0.34 ± 0.013	0.34 ± 0.013	0.34 ± 0.013
P-wave (mV)	0.100 ± 0.005	0.110 ± 0.007	0.100 ± 0.009	0.097 ± 0.004	0.071 ± 0.007	0.096 ± 0.009
P-wave (s)	0.038 ± 0.001	0.039 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.004	0.038 ± 0.002	0.036 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.003
P-Q segment (s)	0.035 ± 0.002	0.035 ± 0.002	0.040 ± 0.004	0.034 ± 0.002	0.033 ± 0.002	0.035 ± 0.002
P-Q interval (s)	0.073 ± 0.003	0.074 ± 0.003	0.080 ± 0.004	0.072 ± 0.003	0.069 ± 0.003	0.075 ± 0.004
Q-wave (mV)	4/0.075	1/0.100			4/0.175	1/0.200
R-wave (mV)	0.377 ± 0.027	0.367 ± 0.027	0.200 ± 0.046	0.171 ± 0.059	0.245 ± 0.023	0.210 ± 0.029
R-wave (s)	0.034 ± 0.002	0.035 ± 0.002	0.030 ± 0.004	0.027 ± 0.004	0.033 ± 0.002	0.029 ± 0.002
S-wave (mV)	4/0.100 ± 0.000	2/0.250 ± 0.150	10/0.185 ± 0.032	0.339 ± 0.021		4/0.112 ± 0.062
S-T segment (s)	0.054 ± 0.002	0.051 ± 0.002	0.048 ± 0.003	0.059 ± 0.003	0.057 ± 0.002	0.055 ± 0.003
Q-T interval (s)	0.158 ± 0.004	0.156 ± 0.005	0.148 ± 0.007	0.158 ± 0.004	0.160 ± 0.002	0.153 ± 0.006
T-wave (mV)	+ 0.171 ± 0.017	+ 0.140 ± 0.010	± 0.087 ± 0.010	- 0.155 ± 0.014	+0.137 ± 0.015	+ 0.097 ± 0.009
T-wave (s)	0.063 ± 0.003	0.056 ± 0.002	0.041 ± 0.003	0.057 ± 0.002	0.054 ± 0.003	0.048 ± 0.002
T-P segment (s)	0.108 ± 0.011	0.106 ± 0.009	0.136 ± 0.017	0.108 ± 0.010	0.109 ± 0.015	0.104 ± 0.012
Systolic indicator %	46.47					
Electric axis	+ 49°					

T-wave was positive in all heart leads except in aVR lead where it was negative. A similar trend was recorded in the second group.

The duration of the T-wave was the highest in the standard lead II 0.050 ± 0.002 s and the lowest in standard leads III and aVL 0.040 ± 0.003 s. The values for this parameter were shown to be higher in leads of a second group of cats without obesity.

The T-P segment had the same duration in all six heart leads and was shown to be shorter compared to the second group.

Systolic indicator was close in value in two groups of clinically healthy cats with and without obesity - respectively 48.75% and 46.47%, and the values for the electric axis of the heart in both groups were close - + 43° to + 49°.

Discussion

Heart rate in obese cats was $188.00 \pm 6.39 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($183.92 \pm 7.39 \text{ min}^{-1}$ without obesity). These values were 9 beats per minute lower than those established by Tilley (1992) 197 min^{-1} (120–240) and in the broader range described by Martin (2005) $160\text{--}240 \text{ min}^{-1}$, but fall within the stated range.

The amplitude R-wave in obese cats did not exceed 0.9 mV, as published by Tilley (1992) and Martin (2005).

The amplitude of the P-wave in overweight cats did not exceed the values of 0.2 mV, as reported by Tilley (1992) and Martin (2005).

The length of the P-wave in cats was close to values of 0.04 s, as indicated by Tilley (1992) and Martin (2005).

The amplitude of the R-wave in the cats of the target group did not exceed values of 0.9 mV, as published by Tilley (1992) and Martin (2005).

The electric heart axis in clinically healthy obese cats is + o. Tilley (1992) and Martin (2005) did not indicate average values for the indicator, but it was within the range of 0° to $+160^\circ$ for cats and the values we calculate for both groups with and without obesity.

The data that we obtained about the length of the P-wave did not match that of Gláucia B.P. et al. (2010) showing an increase in the mean length of the P-wave, and we recorded a shortening compared to the values for the same indicator as compared to the data for non-obese cats.

Conclusion

1. The results that we obtained cannot be compared with results reported by other authors for two reasons:
 - there is no data from other authors that thoroughly examine the values for all ECG elements in six heart leads in clinically healthy cats. The values for some of the items are only highlighted for standard leads
 - the same is true for the values of ECG elements in six heartbeats in the obese group of cats. Here the data is even more scarce, which only allows them to be compared with those for non-obese animals or with those obtained from clinically healthy cats.
2. The P–Q and P–Q values are unreliably elevated in the non-obese group.
3. The amplitude of the R-wave was not found to be lower in the obese group of animals, with the values for the length of the same tooth in the opposite direction. A similar tendency for amplitude and duration follows the T wave compared to the two groups of cats with and without obesity.
4. It was proved that the T-P segment had a lower duration in the group of obese animals than in the group of normal-weight cats.
5. The values of the heart rate, the amplitude, and the duration of the other ECG elements in the six heart lead such as those for the systolic index and the electric axis in both groups of clinically healthy cats with and without obesity were very close.
6. The obtained initial data on ECG elements in overweight clinically healthy cats gave us a good reason to continue the studies in this direction such as looking for a new correlation between the values of the elements and those of heart disease as future prevention.

References

1. Kostov, Y. (1995). *Elektrokardiographia na domashnite zivotni*. NIS – Stara Zagora, 144 p.
2. Martin, M. (2005). *Rukovodstvo po elektrokardiografii melkih domashnih zivotnah*. M., OOO “Akvarium print”, 144 p.
3. Lourenco, M., H. Ferreira. (2003). *Electrocardiographic evolution in cats from birth to 30 days of age*. *Can. Vet. J.*, 44 (11), 914–917.
4. Tilley, L. P. (1992). *Essentials of Canine and Feline electrocardiography: interpretation and treatment*. Third edition, Lea & Febiger, Philadelphia, London, 470 p.
5. Finn E., L.M. Freeman, J.E. Rush, Y. Lee. (2010). *The Relationship Between Body Weight, Body Condition, and Survival in Cats with Heart Failure*. *J Vet Intern Med.*, 24, pp. 1369–1374.
6. Lund E. M., P. J. Armstrong, C. A. Kirk, J. S. Klausner. (2005). *Prevalence and Risk Factors for Obesity in Adult Cats from Private US Veterinary Practices*. *Intern J Appl Res Vet Med.*, Vol. 3, No. 2.
7. Hoenig M. (2012). *The Cat as a Model for Human Obesity and Diabetes*. *J Diabetes Sci Technol.*, 6(3), pp. 525–533.
8. Pereira-Neto G. B., M. A. Brunetto, M. G. Sousa², A. C. Carciofi, A. A. Camacho. (2010). *Effects of weight loss on the cardiac parameters of obese dogs*. *Pesq. Vet. Bras.* 30(2), pp. 167–171.
9. Gláucia B.P. Neto, M. A. Brunetto, M. G. Sousa, A. C. Carciofi and A. A. Camacho. (2010). *Effects of weight loss on the cardiac parameters of obese dogs*. *Pesq. Vet. Bras.* 30(2), pp. 167–171.